

Staphylococcus Aureus Pigment-Bio Colour as a Novel Antibacterial Agent Against Staphylococcus Aureus Isolate from Coins

Ayisha Begum, M. K. Aishwarya, Aeliya Zehra. M, Achiffa Abdul Rahiman, R. Ushasri
P.G. Department of Applied Microbiology, JBAS College for Women, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

The pathogen *Staphylococcus aureus* is Gram-positive cocci in clusters which forms golden colony on Nutrient agar. The most important characteristic feature of *Staphylococcus aureus* is its yellow to orange colour due to production of Staphyloxanthin. Staphyloxanthin is membrane bound Carotenoid and plays an important role in antimicrobial activity. The aim of the present study was to detect the role of Staphyloxanthin pigment production from *S. aureus* isolates against *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate from coin proving antagonistic property. The crude ethanol pigment was used against *Staphylococcus aureus* in different concentrations ranging from 500 μ l to 62.5 μ l by well diffusion method. Minimum inhibition was found to be 11mm at concentration range of 500. μ l. The current study reported that coin plays an important role in transmitting infections

Keywords: *Staphyloxanthin, Carotenoid, MHA, MSA*

INTRODUCTION

The pathogen *Staphylococcus aureus* is Gram-positive cocci in clusters which forms golden colony on Nutrient agar. The most important characteristic feature of *Staphylococcus aureus* is its yellow to orange colour due to production of Staphyloxanthin. Staphyloxanthin is membrane bound carotenoid and plays an important role in antimicrobial activity. Membrane pigments acts as virulence factors in *S. aureus*. Staphyloxanthin is a secondary metabolite produced during stationary phase which has a chemical formula of (C₅₁H₇₈O₈). Staphyloxanthin is a neutral molecule. The aim of the present study was to detect the role of Staphyloxanthin pigment production from *S. aureus* isolates against

Staphylococcus aureus isolate from coin proving antagonistic property. Nutrient agar, Brain Heart infusion agar, Milk agar medium, Pea nut seed medium, Sunflowers seeds medium, Sesame seed medium, Trypticase yeast agar medium, Carotenoid expression agar medium were used for production of staphyloxanthin. The pigment of *Staphylococcus aureus* (STX) was extracted by using Ethanol. Bacterial cells were recovered from the growth on Nutrient agar plate at 37°C. The bacterial cells were centrifuged at 2000rpm for 15 min. Staphyloxanthin from the pellet containing the bacterial cells was collected. The pellet was mixed with 8 ml of 99.9% Ethanol wrapped with aluminum foil to avoid light exposure and kept in oven for 72 hrs to obtain crude extract. Carotenoids were estimated quantitatively by measuring the absorbance of the solution at 450 nm. The crude pigment extracts were evaluated for antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate from coins collected from crowded area.

METHODOLOGY

Sample Collection

The coin were collected in crowded area from petty shop and transport in zip lock cover using sterile hand gloves and transferred to sterile broth for sample processing.

Sample Processing

The samples were then processed by inoculating into the nutrient broth and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C for determining the growth of organism followed by centrifugation. The organisms in the samples were then identified by microscopic, cultural and biochemical tests as *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Coin in nutrient broth

Filtration of centrifuged supernatant broth

Identification of Staphylococcus

Staphylococcus was identified by Gram staining, Hanging drop, catalase, and oxidase tests. The cultural characteristics and biochemical characters were performed to identify Staphylococcus.

Extraction of pigment

The pigmented broth was transferred to sterile tubes and centrifuged for 30 mins at 1500 rpm. The supernatant was filtered by using sterile whats Mann filter paper. The filtrate was extracted using ethanol solvent. The filtrate was evaporated to extract crude pigment and stored in vials for antibacterial activity.

Inoculation of staphylococcus aureus
In to nutrient broth

Crude ethanol pigment extract

Incubation of pigmented broth in rotary shaker at 37°C

MICROSCOPIC APPEARANCE

The inoculated colonies were observed for microscopic appearance and identified as motile gram positive cocci in clusters.

Red pigmented broth after 48 hrs.

Gram positive cocci in clusters

Yellow colonies on Mannitol salt agar

Coagulase positive – S.aureus

Preliminary Tests of Staphylococcus Aureus

Sl. no	Tests	Observation
1.	Gram staining	Gram-Positive cocci in clusters
2.	Motility	Non motile
3.	Catalase	Postive
4.	Oxidase	Negative

Antibiotic sensitivity test for the S. aureus

S.aureus was found highly sensitive to Erythromycin followed by sensitive to clindamycin and vancomycin and resistant to the antibiotic Penicillin.

Sl. no	Antibiotics	Zone of Inhibition
1.	Vancomycin	13 mm
2.	Erythromycin	25 mm
3.	Clindamycin	17 mm
4.	Penicillin	Resistant

Cultural Characters of Staphylococcus Aureus

S. No	Colony morphology	Inference
1.	Size and colour	1-2 mm and yellow colonies
2.	Margin	Entire
3.	Shape	Circular
4.	Opacity	Opaque
5.	Consistency	Smooth
6.	Elevation	Convex

Isolation and identification of Staphylococcus aureus from coin

Biochemical Characters of Staphylococcus Aureus

DNase positive - S.aureus

Gram positive cocci in cluster

Yellow colonies on Mannitol salt agar

Antibiotic sensitivity test for S.aureus isolate from coin

S. aureus was found highly sensitive to Amikacin and resistant to the antibiotics such as Ceftriaxone, Cefixime, Amoxicillin

Sl.No	Antibiotics	Zone Of Inhibition
1.	Vancomycin	13 mm
2.	Erythromycin	25 mm
3.	Clindamycin	17 mm
4.	Penicillin	Resistant

Antibacterial Activity of crude pigment extract

The antibacterial activity of crude ethanol pigment of Staphylococcus aureus was determined by inoculating Staphylococcus aureus isolate into Nutrient broth and incubated for 24 hrs at 37°C. The turbidity of broth was compared to 0.5 N McFarland solutions. The lawn was prepared using Staphylococcus aureus isolate on Muller Hinton agar. The wells were cut using sterile well puncher and one milligram of pigment extract was suspended in 100 µl of acetone and 900 µl nutrient broth. Different concentrations of pigment extracts ranging from 500, 250, 125, 62.5 µl were loaded into wells using water as control. Muller Hinton agar plate was incubated at 37 °C for 24 hrs and observed for Zone formation.

Coagulase test – Positive for isolate from coin

Well diffusion method for- staphylococcus species

DNase test – Positive for isolate Staphylococcus aureus from coin

DISCUSSION

The pathogen Staphylococcus aureus is Gram-positive cocci in clusters which forms golden colony on Nutrient agar. The most important characteristic feature of Staphylococcus aureus is its yellow to orange color due to production of Staphyloxanthin. Staphyloxanthin is membrane bound carotenoid and plays an important role in antimicrobial activity. The main aim of this study was to extract pigment and determine the antibacterial activity against Staphylococcus aureus isolated from coin exchanged among the crowded population. The UV Visible

spectro photometric studies showed highest peak indicating estimation of pigment This study showed that crude acetone pigment extracts exhibited most potent antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate by performing well diffusion using different concentrations of crude pigment extract ranging from 500µl to 62.5 µl exhibiting inhibitory values of 11mm The isolate was found to be resistant to pigment extracts at concentration range of 250 µl 125 µl and 62.5 µl. Minimum bactericidal concentrations was performed and found to be turbid by showing cloudy appearance.

Summary and Conclusion

Staphyloxanthin is a secondary metabolite produced by *Staphylococcus aureus* during stationary phase which has a chemical formula of (C₅₁H₇₈O₈). Staphyloxanthin is a neutral molecule. The aim of the present study was to detect the role of Staphyloxanthin pigment production from *S. aureus* isolates against *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate from coin proving low antagonistic property. *Staphylococcus aureus* was sub cultured and inoculated in to Nutrient broth followed by incubation at 37°C for 48 hrs in rotary shaker for production of pigment. The pigmented broth was centrifuged at 1500 rpm for 30 mins. The supernatant was filtered using sterile what Mann filter paper. The filtrate was mixed with ethanol and kept in oven overnight to obtain crude extract. The crude extract was stored in sterile storage vials for antibacterial study. The coin was collected from public transport in crowded area and transferred to sterile Zip lock cover using sterile hand gloves. The coin was transferred to nutrient broth in flask and incubated at 37°C. The turbidity was observed and microscopic examination was done by Gram staining technique and found to be Gram positive cocci in clusters. The broth culture was inoculated in to Nutrient agar and Mannitol salt agar and incubated for 24 hrs at 37°C. Coagulase and DNase tests were performed to differentiate *Staphylococcus* spp. Antibiotic sensitivity tests was done to find out sensitivity of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate to antibiotics. The isolate was found to be highly resistant to Penicillin and sensitive to Erythromycin. The crude ethanol pigment was used against *staphylococcus aureus* in different concentrations ranging from 500µl to 62.5 µl by well diffusion method. Maximum inhibition was found to be at different concentrations were found to be 11mm at concentration range of 500. µl .The current study reported that coin plays an important role s

transmitting infections .It was concluded that coin acts as one of the factors for spread of infections. The Staphyloxanthin acts as an important antagonist and is a novel bio colour against *Staphylococcus aureus* isolate from coins. This study was done for the first time to the best of our Knowledge.

Acknowledgements

The Authors thank Ms Summera Rafiq, Associate Professor & Head, P.G. Dept of Applied Microbiology for her valuable support and Ms Tharani. V of M. Sc II nd year, Microbiology for extended help in providing culture,

REFERENCES

1. Daum, R. S. 2008 Removing the golden coat of *Staphylococcus aureus* N. Engl. J. Med. 359, pp: 85–87
2. Marshall, J. H., and G. J. Wilmoth. 1981. Proposed pathway of triterpenoid carotenoid biosynthesis in *Staphylococcus aureus*: evidence from a study of mutants. J. Bacteriol. 147, pp: 914-919
3. Clauditz A, Resch A.; Wieland KP, Peschel A and Götz F 2006. Staphyloxanthin plays a role in the fitness of *Staphylococcus aureus* and its ability to cope with oxidative stress. Infect. Immun., 74(8), pp: 4950-4953
4. Pelz A, Wieland KP, Putzbach K, Hentschel P, Albert K, Götz F 2005. Structure and biosynthesis of staphyloxanthin from *Staphylococcus aureus*. J. Biol Chem. 280(37):32493-32498
5. Liu CI, Liu GY, Song Y, Yin F, Hensler ME, Jeng WY, Nizet V, Wang AH, Oldfield E 2008. "A cholesterol biosynthesis inhibitor blocks *Staphylococcus aureus* virulence". Science 319 (5868) pp: 391–94.
6. Rohmer, M., P. Bouvier, and G. Ourisson. 1979. Molecular evolution of membranes: structural equivalents and phylogenetic precursors of sterols. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A. 76 pp: 847– 851
7. Pelz A, Wieland KP, Putzbach K, Hentschel P, Albert K, Götz F 2005. Structure and biosynthesis of staphyloxanthin from *Staphylococcus aureus*. J Biol Chem. 280(37) pp: 32493-32498 Al-Kazaz et. Al. Iraqi Journal of Science, 2014, Vol 55, No.4B, pp:1823-1832 1831
8. Hartmann, W., and H. J. Galla. 1978. Binding of polylysine to charged bilayer membranes:

- molecular organization of a lipid peptide complex. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 509, pp: 474–490.
9. Kim, J., M. Mosior, L. A. Chung, H. Wu, and S. McLaughlin. 1991. Binding of peptides with basic residues to membranes containing acidic phospholipids. *Biophys. J.* 60 pp:135–148.
 10. Hammond, R. K. and White, D. C. 1970. Carotenoid Formation by *Staphylococcus aureus*. *J. of Bacteriol.* 103(1) pp: 191-198
 11. William, B. W; Paul D.V. George, M. G. Dorothy, J. Noel R. K. Wolfgang, L. Fred, A. R. and Karl, S. 2009. *Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology* 2nd edition Com.pp: .392-433.
 12. Grinsted, J., and Lacey R. C 1973. Ecological and genetic implications of pigmentation in *Staphylococcus aureus*. *J. Gen. Microbiol.* 75 pp: 259-267.
 13. Marshall JH, Wilmoth GJ. 1981. Pigments of *Staphylococcus aureus*, a series of triterpenoid carotenoids. *J Bacteriol*; 147 pp: 900-913.
 14. Wieland B, Feil C, Gloria-Maercker E, Thumm G, Lechner M, Bravo JM, Poralia K, Götz F 1994. Genetic and biochemical analyses of the biosynthesis of the yellow carotenoid 4,4'-diaponeurosporene of *Staphylococcus aureus*. *J. Bacteriol.*, 176(24) pp: 7719-7726.
 15. Tao, N. Gao, Y. Liu, Y. and Ge, F. 2010. Carotenoids from the Peel of Shatian Pummelo (*Citrus grandis* Osbeck) and Antimicrobial Activity. *American Eurasian J. Agric & Environ. Sci.*, 7(1) pp: 110-115.

